

TASHKENT CITY ATMOSPHERIC AIR QUALITY INDICATORS ANALYSIS

(On the example of Yakkasaroy and Sergeli districts)

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Introduction: one of the most important tasks facing humanity today is to protect the environment and maintain human health [1]. While being one of the objects of the environment is atmospheric air. It is no secret that industrial, production and automobile vehicles negatively affect the air quality of large cities [2]. The increase in the negative impact of economic, social and political development factors on the environment in the world economy will certainly increase the number of side effects on human health and serve as the cause of the origin of various non-infectious diseases. The research work covered two existing districts in the city of Tashkent: Sergeli as an observation district, which is now a construction site and is developing industry, as well as Yakkasaroy district as a control region, which includes many greened areas, relatively few industrial enterprises.

Research materials and method: 2017, 2018 and 2019 Sergeli and Yakkasaroy district atmospheric air quality indicators of the sanitary epidemiological tranquility and public health service of the city of Tashkent used annual analysis data, and the data obtained was assessed hygienically using descriptive, statistical and analytical methods.

Research results: a total of 1238 samples were taken for 2017 atmospheric air quality analysis when the results of a laboratory examination of the level of atmospheric air pollution of the Yakkasaroy District Department of the sanitary

epidemiological tranquility and Public Health Service (CEO and JS) were analyzed. According to the report, atmospheric air samples were an indicator of pollution, containing organic and non-organic contaminants such as sulfur oxide, hydrogen sulfide, carbon monoxide, nitric oxide, ammonia, formaldehyde, sulfuric acid, chlorine and its compounds, heavy metals, acetone. But of all the samples taken, only non-standard samples were observed in the indicator of air pollution. Samples taken for the pollution factor accounted for 480 (38.7%) of the total samples, of which 227 (47.2%) had above-normal levels. In other indicators presented above, cases of increase in Norm are not identified. Non-standard samples have also been identified at pollution level only in terms of metrics provided for 2018 and 2019, i.e. a total of 1,226 samples were taken in 2018, of which 480 (39.2%) were taken for pollution, of which 211 (43.9%), and a total of 2019 of 1,160 samples were taken for pollution, of which 478 (41.2%) were identified non-standard samples in 190 (39.7%).

The same indicators were studied based on the data of the Sergeli District Department of sanitary and epidemiological tranquility and Public Health Service of the quality of atmospheric air in the Sergeli District, which is located in the city of Tashkent and is now a center of many construction works and is home to many industrial enterprises. A total of 1,902 samples were taken for 2017 atmospheric air quality analysis, a total of 1,950 in 2018 and a total of 1,677 in 2019, and analyzed in the sanitary and hygienic laboratory. Of a total of 1,902 samples taken in 2017, 416 (21.8%) were taken for pollution level analysis and 27.6% (115) of it were cited to exceed established norm requirements (recs). In addition 416 samples were taken for sulfur oxides in the same year, accounting for 21.8 % (416) of the total sample, and 75 (18%) of it exceeded the norm requirement. For hydrogen sulfide, 88 samples (4.6%) were taken, and the proportion of non-standard samples was 5 (5.6%), of the 496 samples for nitrogen oxides, 66 (13.3%) of it accounted for the proportion of non-standard samples. A total of

1,950 samples were taken when the data presented in 2018 were analyzed, of which 404 (20.7%) were taken to determine pollination (the proportion of non-standard samples is 141 i.e. 35%), 436 (22.3%) were taken to identify sulfur oxides (the proportion of non-standard samples is 89 i.e.20.4%), 101 (5.2%) were used to identify hydrogen sulfide (the proportion of non-standard samples is 4 4.7%) SI for the determination of carbon monoxide (the proportion of non-standard samples is 4 or 4.3%), 436 si (41.5%) for the determination of nitrogen oxides (the number of non-standard samples is 81 or 18.8%) if obtained, to determine the ammonia and formaldehyde indicators, 39 (2%) and 44 (2.25%) samples were taken, respectively, of which the proportion of non-standard samples was 2, which is 5.1% and 4.5% of the sample taken. According to a 2019 data analysis, a total of 1,677 samples were taken in the same year, and 198 of the total sample (11.8%) accounted for the share of non-standard samples. In particular, 370 samples (22%) were taken for pollination, of which 83 (22.4%) per share of Si non-standard samples. 330 (19.6%) samples were taken to detect sulfur oxides, of which 62 (18.7%) did not meet the norm requirements. 96 samples (5.7%) were taken to detect hydrogen sulfide, of which 10 or 10.4% were non-standard samples. In addition to these, 322 (19.2%) samples were taken to detect nitrogen oxides, and the proportion of non-standard samples in it was 43 (13.3%). In sergeli district, 228, 272 and 244 samples were taken in 2017, 2018 and 2019 in an appropriate way to detect heavy metals from atmospheric air, and non-standard samples were not detected in all years.

Conclusion: In conclusion, when the atmospheric air quality indicators of Yakkasaroy and Sergeli districts were analyzed on the basis of data from the district departments of the SEO and JS service for 2017, 2018 and 2019, it was found that the level of atmospheric air pollution of Sergeli district is significantly higher than that of Yakkasaroy district on organic and non-organic contaminants such as sulfur oxide, hydrogen sulfide, carbon monoxide, ammonia,

formaldehyde, sulfuric acid, heavy metals, acetone. But according to the pollution indicator, it was found that the pollution level in Yakkasaroy district was 1.53 times higher than in Sergeli district.

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